

unsaponifiable matter and esterification of the sample with 4% hydrochloric acid in methanol at 70-90° for 12-14 h³. Different fatty acids in the form of methyl esters were analysed through glc. The operating conditions of glc were: Pye-Unticam 204 instrument, Reoplex glass column (6 mm × 2 m), F.I.D. detector, nitrogen flow rate 35 ml min⁻¹, column temperature 180, isothermal condition, injection port temperature 270, detector 300. Peak area was calculated by triangulation method. Physical characteristics of the seed oil were studied by the reported method⁴.

The seeds contain 7.2% oil. Physical characteristics of the oil were: refractive index 1.472, iodine value 107, saponification value 193. The unsaponifiable matter found to be 4.5% is quite high in comparison to other reported Indian gram varieties⁵.

Results and Discussion

Among the various fatty acids, linoleic acid predominated (37.13%). Stearic, lauric and linolenic acids were found to be 25.38, 23.05 and 6.10%, respectively, while myristic, palmitic and arachidic acids were in lesser concentrations. The glc graph (Fig. 1) showed two unidentified peaks, one after lauric acid (peak-I) and other after palmitic acid (peak-II) whose concentrations were 3.4 and 2.18%, respectively. It is significant to note that *C. soongaricum* seeds oil is a rich source of essential fatty acids, viz. linoleic and linolenic acids (43.23%). In addition of fulfilling dietary requirements, the essential fatty acids are also precursors in the biosynthesis of prostaglandins which in trace amounts are necessary for various physiological activities.

Acknowledgement

Grateful thanks are due to the Department of Environment, Government of India, New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

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Chemical Investigation of *Holoptelea integrifolia* Planch. and *Cassia fistula* Linn.

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Manuscript received 23 August 1985, accepted 24 December 1985

HOLOPTELEA *integrifolia* Planch. (Ulmaceae) is the only species of the genus *Holoptelea* occurring in India. Several triterpenoids¹⁻³, aliphatic

alcohols¹ and acids⁴ were isolated from this plant. *Cassia fistula* Linn. (Leguminosae) is one of the commonest trees of India. All its parts were previously investigated and several anthraquinones⁵⁻¹⁰, flavonoids^{6,7,9}, and aliphatic alcohols^{5,11}, acids¹¹ and esters¹¹ were isolated. Both these plants have medicinal uses^{12,13}. Reinvestigation of the stem bark of *H. integrifolia* has resulted in the isolation of 2-aminonaphthaquinone (yield, 0.0013%), friedelin (0.002%), epifriedelinol (0.0053%), β -sitosterol (0.004%) and its β -D-glucoside (0.01%), while that of the flowers of *C. fistula* yielded aurantiamide acetate (0.011%), β -sitosterol (0.006%), its β -D-glucoside (0.02%) and an uncharacterised fatty acid ester of β -sitosterol (CF-1) (0.001%). Although 2-aminonaphthaquinone is synthetically known¹⁴, to our knowledge, there is no previous report of its natural occurrence.

Holoptelea integrifolia Planch. :

Air dried and powdered stem bark of *H. integrifolia* (1.5 kg), collected from Midnapore district in West Bengal during October was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus for 40 h each first with petroleum ether and then with chloroform. The petroleum ether extract on concentration and cooling deposited a yellowish white solid which was collected by filtration. Chromatography of the solid on a silica gel column gave friedelin (eluate: petroleum ether-benzene, 1:1) and epifriedelinol (benzene), and that of the concentrate of the filtrate furnished the same two compounds and β -sitosterol (benzene-chloroform, 1:1). The concentrate of the chloroform extract on similar chromatography afforded 2-aminonaphthaquinone (chloroform-methanol, 49:1) and β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside (chloroform-methanol, 9:1).

2-Aminonaphthaquinone crystallised in orange-red needles, m.p. 205° (lit.¹⁴ 205°) from chloroform-petroleum ether; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) (log ϵ) 233 (3.98), 266 (4.19), 333 (3.20) and 445 nm (3.44); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3370-3180 (NH), 1685 (C=O), 1625, 1570, 1420, 1365, 1270, 1220, 1125, 980, 825 and 720 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 5.16 (2H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, 2-NH₂), 5.97 (1H, s, H-3), 7.55-7.78 (2H, m, H-6 and H-7) and 7.97-8.11 (2H, m, H-5 and H-8); *m/e* (rel. int.) 173 (100, M⁺), 146 (93, M-HCN), 145 (49, M-CO), 118 (43, M-HCN-CO), 117 (93, M-2CO), 105 (96, M-HCN-CHCO), 104 (91, M-HCN-CH₂CO), 77 (88) and 76 (79). On treatment with ethanolic 0.5 N HCl, 2-aminonaphthaquinone furnished 2-hydroxynaphthaquinone, crystallising from chloroform-petroleum ether as yellow needles, m.p. 150° d (lit.¹⁵ 192° d). The formation of 2-hydroxynaphthaquinone by acid hydrolysis of 2-aminonaphthaquinone indicates that the latter behaves as a vinylogous amide, not as an amine. The insolubility of 2-aminonaphthaquinone in dilute acids and its resistance to acetylation at room temperature with acetic anhydride and pyridine also support this view.

The other isolates were identified by direct comparison with their authentic samples as well as their spectral data (ir, uv, nmr, etc.).

Cassia fistula Linn. :

Air dried and powdered flowers of *C. fistula* (1 kg), collected from Midnapore district of West Bengal in May were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus for 40 h each with petroleum ether and chloroform successively. The petroleum ether extract on concentration and cooling deposited a solid which was separated by filtration. Chromatography of the solid over a silica gel column gave aurantiamide acetate (eluate : chloroform-methanol, 49 : 1) and that of the concentrate of the filtrate gave CF-1, an uncharacterised fatty acid ester of β -sitosterol (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 1), and β -sitosterol (benzene). The concentrate of the chloroform extract on column chromatography over silica gel afforded a further amount of aurantiamide acetate along with β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside (chloroform-methanol, 9 : 1).

Aurantiamide acetate, a modified phenylalanine dipeptide, crystallising from chloroform-petroleum ether as clusters of hairy needles, m.p. 185° (lit¹⁶, 185°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -44^\circ$ (c 0.12 in CHCl₃), was identified from its spectral properties and finally by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹⁶. The ir spectrum of CF-1 indicated the presence of an ester C=O (1735 cm⁻¹) and its ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited signals at δ 1.22 (~24H, s), 2.23 (2H, t, J 6 Hz) and 4.3-4.7 (1H, m). Its hydrolysis with ethanolic 1N HCl afforded β -sitosterol. Thus, CF-1 appeared to be an ester of β -sitosterol and a fatty acid. It could not be characterised owing to paucity of material.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Professor S. K. Talapatra of this Department, for providing an authentic sample of aurantiamide acetate, and are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (H.M.).

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Chemical Investigation of *Alstonia congensis* Engl.—Isolation of Rhazine

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Manuscript received 23 September 1985,
accepted 17 February 1986

THE major source of indole alkaloids in nature are plants belonging to different genera of the family Apocynaceae. Several species of the genus *Alstonia* (family: Apocynaceae) occur widely in tropical countries of Asia and Africa. The extract of different species of this genus are reputed as antimalarials and in many cases as a tonic for general debility. In the present communication we report the systematic investigation of the stem-bark of *Alstonia congensis* and the characterisation of one of the constituent alkaloids as rhazine¹ (1).

Sun-dried stem-bark of *Alstonia congensis* (collected from Africa) was powdered, defatted with petrol and then extracted with methanol at room temperature for 20 days. The concentrated methanolic extract was churned with aqueous 5% citric acid solution and the mixture filtered. The aqueous extract was basified with NH₃ solution at 0° to pH 9 and extracted with chloroform. The concentrated chloroform extract was chromatographed over alumina. An alkaloid, C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₃ (M⁺ 352), m.p. 235-36° d, was obtained from the benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluates. Its mass spectrum showed prominent peaks at *m/z* 352 (M⁺), 351 (M-1), 337 (M-CH₃), 321 (M-OCH₃/CH₂OH), 170, 169, 168 and 154, respectively. The latter fragments are characteristic of the tetrahydro- β -carboline moiety. Its uv spectrum further corroborated this view, showing λ_{max} at 291, 280-283 and 227 nm (log ϵ 3.78, 3.87 and 4.52) which suffered a hypsochromic shift to 290, 273-274 and 222 nm (log ϵ 3.81, 3.93 and 4.56) in presence of a trace of acid. It showed ir bands at 3150-3400 (br, OH), 1705 and 1215 (ester C=O), 1445, 840 and 730 cm⁻¹, respectively. The spectroscopical data (uv, ir, ms, ¹H nmr) indicated that the alkaloid was probably identical with rhazine¹.